

Paper 21

SECURITY SOLUTIONS ON NETWORKS - ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

Communication and Resource Sharing are the major goals of any networks. But due to its open internetwork architecture, there are several threats on our system and hence system designers should implement several security mechanisms to counter any such attacks. Security over any network can be implemented at various levels starting from level 0 till upper most level. Mechanisms like Packet Filtering at Frame level, Switch Security, Router Security and Application Gateways along with Firewalls are the few security solutions that one can adopt while implementing a secured network system. This paper will discuss on these different design practices and the levels of security achieved by them.

Keywords: Communication, Packet Filtering, Firewall, Application Gateway

1. Introduction

Communication Network is the system made out of Hardware as well as Software collectively to meet the objective of Communication and Resource Sharing[2]. The whole process of communication needs to be guided within the framework of restricted time frame, cost and errors. Complicated systems have been built up to serve these issues of communication. But such systems were open to interconnect and were pron towards possible attacks from the third party. Hence complexity of such communication systems have been further refined so as to cunter such kind of attacks from intruders. Network security[3] is an activity which protects the usability and integrity of the network and also the data, including both hardware and software technologies. Effective network security implementation will manage the network access. It counters variety of threats and stops them from entering and spreading on the network. Network security deploys multiple layers of defenses at the edge and in the network. In each of the network security layer it implements right policies and controls. Hence only authorized users gain access to network resources and intruders are blocked from carrying out threats. In this paper firstly we will discussing the different possible attacks on Network Systems and the various counter measures that has been in place to protect the Network Systems.

2. Network Attacks

There are varities of network attacks to which any system is exposed in the public domaine. We will be listing few of such attacks and their significance.

Malware – short for malicious software which is specifically designed to disrupt, damage, or gain authorized access to a computer system. Much of the malware out there today is self-replicating: once it infects one host, from that host it seeks entry into other hosts over the Internet, and from the newly infected hosts, it seeks entry into yet more hosts. In this manner,

self-replicating malware can spread exponentially fast.

Virus – A malware which requires some form of user's interaction to infect the user's device. The classic example is an e-mail attachment containing malicious executable code. If a user receives and opens such an attachment, the user inadvertently runs the malware on the device.

Worm – A malware which can enter a device without any explicit user interaction. For example, a user may be running a vulnerable network application to which an attacker can send malware. In some cases, without any user intervention, the application may accept the malware from the Internet and run it, creating a worm.

Botnet – A network of private computers infected with malicious software and controlled as a group without the owners' knowledge, e.g. to send spam.

DoS (Denial of Service) – A DoS attack renders a network, host, or other pieces of infrastructure unusable by legitimate users. Most Internet DoS attacks fall into one of three categories

- *Vulnerability attack*: This involves sending a few well-crafted messages to a vulnerable application or operating system running on a targeted host. If the right sequence of packets is sent to a vulnerable application or operating system, the service can stop or, worse, the host can crash.

- *Bandwidth flooding*: The attacker sends a deluge of packets to the targeted host—so many packets that the target's access link becomes clogged, preventing legitimate packets from reaching the server.

- *Connection flooding*: The attacker establishes a large number of half-open or fully open TCP connections at the target host. The host can become so bogged down with these bogus connections that it stops accepting legitimate connections.

DDoS (Distributed DoS) – DDoS is a type of DOS attack where multiple compromised systems, are used to target a single system causing a Denial of Service (DoS) attack. DDoS attacks leveraging botnets with thousands of comprised hosts are a common occurrence today. DDoS attacks are much harder to detect and defend against than a DoS attack from a single host.

Packet sniffer – A passive receiver that records a copy of every packet that flies by is called a packet sniffer. By placing a passive receiver in the vicinity of the wireless transmitter, that receiver can obtain a copy of every packet that is transmitted! These packets can contain all kinds of sensitive information, including passwords, social security numbers, trade secrets, and private personal messages. Some of the best defenses against packet sniffing involve cryptography.

IP Spoofing – The ability to inject packets into the Internet with a false source address is known as IP spoofing, and is but one of many ways in which one user can masquerade as another user. To solve this problem, we will need end-point authentication, that is, a mechanism that will allow us to determine with certainty if a message originates from where we think it does.

Man-in-the-Middle Attack – As the name indicates, a man-in-the-middle attack occurs when someone between you and the person with whom you are communicating is actively monitoring, capturing, and controlling your communication transparently. For example, the attacker can re-route a data exchange. When computers are communicating at low levels of the network layer, the computers might not be able to determine with whom they are exchanging data.

Compromised-Key Attack – A key is a secret code or number necessary to interpret secured information. Although obtaining a key is a difficult and resource-intensive process for an

attacker, it is possible. After an attacker obtains a key, that key is referred to as a compromised key. An attacker uses the compromised key to gain access to a secured communication without the sender or receiver being aware of the attack.

Phishing – The fraudulent practice of sending emails purporting to be from reputable companies in order to induce individuals to reveal personal information, such as passwords and credit card numbers.

DNS spoofing – Also referred to as DNS cache poisoning, is a form of computer security hacking in which corrupt Domain Name System data is introduced into the DNS resolver's cache, causing the name server to return an incorrect IP address.

3. Security Solutions

There are varieties of network Security Solutions for such attacks on systems exposed in the public domain. We will be listing few of such Security Solutions and their significance.

Firewalls

Firewalls put up a barrier between your trusted internal network and untrusted outside networks, such as the Internet. They use a set of defined rules to allow or block traffic. A firewall can be hardware, software, or both.

Email Security

Email gateways are the number one threat vector for a security breach. Attackers use personal information and social engineering tactics to build sophisticated phishing campaigns to deceive recipients and send them to sites serving up malware. An email security application blocks incoming attacks and controls outbound messages to prevent the loss of sensitive data.

Antivirus and Antimalware Software

"Malware," short for "malicious software," includes viruses, worms, Trojans, ransomware, and spyware. Sometimes malware will infect a network but lie dormant for days or even weeks. The best antimalware programs not only scan for malware upon entry, but also continuously track files afterward to find anomalies, remove malware, and fix damage.

Network Segmentation

Software-defined segmentation puts network traffic into different classifications and makes enforcing security policies easier. Ideally, the classifications are based on endpoint identity, not mere IP addresses. You can assign access rights based on role, location, and more so that the right level of access is given to the right people and suspicious devices are contained and remediated.

Access Control

Not every user should have access to your network. To keep out potential attackers, you need to recognize each user and each device. Then you can enforce your security policies. You can block noncompliant endpoint devices or give them only limited access. This process is network access control (NAC).

Application Security

Any software you use to run your business needs to be protected, whether your IT staff builds it or whether you buy it. Unfortunately, any application may contain holes, or vulnerabilities, that attackers can use to infiltrate your network. Application security encompasses the hardware, software, and processes you use to close those holes.

Behavioral Analytics

To detect abnormal network behavior, you must know what normal behavior looks like. Behavioral analytics tools automatically discern activities that deviate from the norm. Your security team can then better identify indicators of compromise that pose a potential problem and quickly remediate threats.

Data Loss Prevention

Organizations must make sure that their staff does not send sensitive information outside the network. Data loss prevention, or DLP, technologies can stop people from uploading, forwarding, or even printing critical information in an unsafe manner.

Intrusion Prevention Systems

An Intrusion Prevention System (IPS) scans network traffic to actively block attacks. Cisco Next-Generation IPS (NGIPS) appliances do this by correlating huge amounts of global threat intelligence to not only block malicious activity but also track the progression of suspect files and malware across the network to prevent the spread of outbreaks and reinfection.

Mobile Device Security

Cybercriminals are increasingly targeting mobile devices and apps. Within the next 3 years, 90 percent of IT organizations may support corporate applications on personal mobile devices. Of course, you need to control which devices can access your network. You will also need to configure their connections to keep network traffic private.

Security Information and Event Management

SIEM products pull together the information that your security staff needs to identify and respond to threats. These products come in various forms, including physical and virtual appliances and server software.

VPN

A virtual private network encrypts the connection from an endpoint to a network, often over the Internet. Typically, a remote-access VPN uses IPsec or Secure Sockets Layer to authenticate the communication between device and network.

Web Security

A web security solution will control your staff's web use, block web-based threats, and deny access to malicious websites. It will protect your web gateway on site or in the cloud. "Web security" also refers to the steps you take to protect your own website.

Wireless Security

Wireless networks are not as secure as wired ones. Without stringent security measures, installing a wireless LAN can be like putting Ethernet ports everywhere, including the parking lot. To prevent an exploit from taking hold, you need products specifically designed to protect a wireless network.

4. Conclusion

Though the objective of any Communication Network is achieving Communication and Resource Sharing, due to its open internetwork architecture, there are several threats on such network systems and hence network designers should implement several security mechanisms to counter any such attacks. Attacks like IP Spoofing, DOS, Packet Sniffing,

DNS Spoofing etc are the most commonly used approaches by any intruder to gain unauthorised access to such networks. Designers should deploy security mechanisms at various levels of communication network right from Physical to Application. Approaches like Network Segmentation, Firewalls, ACLs, IPS, SIEM etc, are the usual security implementations that protects not only the networks but also the network users.

References

- [1]. Subrahmanya B & Dr. V. Vijayakumar. "Implementation of Directory based Cache Coherency Model to Analyze the Network Performance in Distributed Applications". IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN), October 2018, vol. 08, Issue 10, pp. 62-68, ISSN (e) 2250-3021, ISSN (p): 2278-8719.
- [2]. Subrahmanya B & Dr. V. Vijayakumar. "Adaptive Directory based Cache Coherency Model to Optimize the Network Bandwidth in Distributed Applications". IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN), September 2018, vol. 08, Issue 9, pp. 41-46, ISSN (e) 2250-3021, ISSN (p): 2278-8719.
- [3]. Shou-Chih Lo, Jih-Sian Hu, Varsha A. Kshirsagar. "Neighborhood-Based In-Network Caching for Information-Centric Networks". Int. J. Communications, Network and System Sciences, 2017, vol.10, pp. 76-87.
- [4]. Sarah Tasneem 1, Reda Ammar 2. "Performance Study of a Distributed Web Server: An Analytical Approach". Journal of Software Engineering and Applications, 2012, vol.5, pp. 855-863.
- [5]. Rizik M. H. Al-Sayyed, Fawaz A. Al Zaghoul, Dima Suleiman, Mariam Itriq, Ismail Hababeh. "New Approach for Database Fragmentation and Allocation to Improve the Distributed Database Management System Performance". Journal of Software Engineering and Applications, 2014, vol.7, pp. 891-905.
- [6]. Hang Qin, Li Zhu. "Adaptive Cache Allocation with Prefetching Policy over End-to-End Data Processing". Journal of Signal and Information Processing, 2017, vol.8, pp. 152-160.
- [7]. Arif Sari, Murat Akkaya. "Fault Tolerance Mechanisms in Distributed Systems". Int. J. Communications, Network and System Sciences, 2015, vol. 8, pp. 471-482.
- [8]. Subrahmanya Bhat & Dr. K. R. Kamath. "Directory Organizations in Cache Coherency

- Systems for High Performance Computation”. International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME), August 2016, vol. I, Issue I, pp. 868-871, ISSN: 2455–5428.
- [9]. Subrahmanya Bhat & Dr. K. R. Kamath. “Directory Based Cache Coherency Protocol In Multi-Core System For High Performance Computation”. International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, May 2016, vol. I, Issue I, pp. 257-261, ISSN:2455–5428.
- [10]. Subrahmanya Bhat B and Dr. K.R Kamath. “Cache Hierarchy In Modern Processors and its Impact On Computing”. International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE), July 2015, vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 248-253, ISSN: 2249-0558, I.F. 5. 299.
- [11]. Subrahmanya Bhat B and Dr. K.R Kamath. “Directory Based Cache Coherency, Organization, Operations And Challenges In Implementation –Study”. International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology (IJATET), 2015, vol. 1, Issue 1, pp. 30-33.
- [12]. Subrahmanya Bhat, & Dr. K. R. Kamath. “Effective Learning With Usage of Simulators – A Case of Nctuns Simulator In Computer Networks”. International journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, 2016, vol. I, Issue I, pp. 415-420. ISSN-2455 – 5630.
- [13]. S.Y. Wang and H.T. Kung. “A New Methodology for Easily Constructing Extensible and High-Fidelity TCP/IP Network Simulators,” Computer Networks, October 2002, Vol. 40, Issue 2, pp. 257-278.
- [14]. S.Y. Wang, C.L. Chou, C.H. Huang, C.C. Hwang, Z.M. Yang, C.C. Chiou, and C.C. Lin. “The Design and Implementation of NCTUns 1.0 Network Simulator,” Computer Networks, June 2003, Vol. 42, Issue 2, pp.175-197.
- [15]. Dimitris Tsaliagos. “Design and Implementation of a Directory based Cache Coherence Protocol”. Technical Report FORTH-ICS/TR-418 May 2011.
- [16]. S.Y. Wang. (July 2003). “NCTUns 1.0,” in the column “Software Tools for Networking,” IEEE Networks, Vol. 17, No. 4.
- [17]. Michel Dubois, Member- IEEE, and Faye A. Briggs, Member-IEEE. “Effects of cache coherency in Multiprocessors”. Technical Report FORTH-ICS/TR-206 May 2011.